

**DETERMINATION OF CHARACTERISTICS FOR THE FORMATION OF
REQUIREMENTS STREAMS IN THE SYSTEM OF MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR OF
MACHINES**

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Mulberry silkworms, which belong to the class of insects, differ from warm-blooded animal species by a number of biological features. The first characteristic of the silkworm is that it belongs to the genus Paykilotherm, which is a cold-blooded organism. Therefore, silkworms need to create certain environmental conditions during their growth and development. Because the body does not have its own temperature, silkworms are also affected by slight changes in external conditions, and the change can increase or decrease its productivity.

The study of the effects of temperature on the realization of the genetic potential of beneficial animals, including silkworms, is of great scientific and practical importance in biology, especially in agriculture.

N.A. Akhmedov (1992), based on his many years of experience in the physiology of mulberry silkworms, said that silkworms are never exposed to the same air temperature and relative humidity during the day. However, changes in the air temperature in the worm from the norm (25-26°C), ie low (20-21°C) or high (28-29°C) are negative not only for the growth and development of worms, but also for the growth dynamics of the silkworm. as long as it has an effect.

U.N.Nasirillaev (1993), based on special experiments, notes that the following temperature and relative humidity have a positive effect on the age of industrial worms:

- When feeding young (I, II, III) worms, the temperature in the wormhole is 26-27 ° C, relative humidity is 65-75%;

- In the care of large (IV, V) age worms temperature 24-25°C, humidity 65-70%;

- keeping the temperature in the cocoon wrapping at 25-26°C, humidity in the range of 60-70%, according to the authors, the described temperature and relative humidity regime gives positive results.

Table 1

The effect of changes in the temperature of the worm on the survival of the worm and the activity of the silkworm. impact on activities

Options	Air temperature in the cage, °S	Prolonged feeding period, days	Worm viability,% $X \pm Sx$	Silk cloth indicators (before cocoon wrapping)		Pd
				Weight, mg	Size, sm ³	
Ipakchi-1 breed						
V ₇	25-26	23	94,5±0,93	1450	1,47	-
V ₈	20-21	30	88,0±0,70	1300	1,30	0,984
V ₉	28-29	20	84,0±0,68	1180	1,20	0,980
Ipakchi-2 breed						
V ₁₀	25-26	23	95,0±0,95	1500	1,52	-
V ₁₁	20-21	30	88,5±0,78	1350	1,35	0,992
V ₁₂	28-29	20	85,0±0,71	1250	1,25	0,988

According to the rules of agronomics, when feeding worms, the temperature in the wormhole is 25-26°C, which is moderate for larvae. However, under production conditions, worm feeders will always lower or raise the temperature in the wormhole without paying attention to this norm. This has a strong effect on the development of worms, especially the viability and activity of the silk glands. The results of this experiment are shown in Table 1 below.

The figures in Table 1 show that below or above the normal temperature in the larvae has a negative impact on the life activity of the silkworm in the postembryonic period. For example, when larvae are fed at a temperature of 20-21°C, their larval period is extended to 30 days, their viability is 88.0-88.5%, when fed at 28-29°C, the larval period is shortened (lasting 20 days), their viability is 84.0-85.0%. The survival rate of worms fed at normal air temperature (25-26°C) at 0% is 94.5-95.0%, the worm cycle is 23 days, and the survival rate is 6.5-10 compared to other options. , Increased by 0%, and the worm period was shortened to 7-10 days.

Thus, the results of experiments on the effect of temperature changes in the worm on the survival of worms show that the temperature in the room below or above the norm in the care of worms slows down or accelerates the metabolic process in silkworms, resulting in disruption of physiological processes. the worms weaken. Especially when the temperature rises, the worms become restless and suffocate, lose body water and development is impaired, resulting in worms becoming ill.

In addition to studying the growth, development, and biological characteristics of the larvae during worm feeding, it was also observed what diseases they may be exposed to under the influence of changes in nutrient content and temperature. Investigations have shown that due to malnutrition, worms lag behind in development, become large and small, and at the age of 4-5 years are susceptible to bacterial (plague and lice) diseases.

Worms are susceptible to fungal and yellow fever when the temperature is below normal (20-210 ° C), and to hemorrhage and plague when the temperature is high (28-290 ° C).

Based on the above data, it should be noted that timely and complete feeding of larvae during the feeding of worms, moderate maintenance of air temperature in the wormhole, the smooth development of worms, high viability and the activity of the silk glands. The biological indicators, productivity and variety of cocoons are high.

REFERENCES:

- 1.N.Axmedov. Ipak qurti ekologiyasi va boqish agrotexnikasi. Darslik. T.2014 y.
2. Yo.Ya.Mirzayeva. “Tut ipak qurti biologiyasi”. Darslik. T. 2017 y.
- 3.Ch.I.Bekkamov., U.T.Daniyarov., N.K.Abdukayumova., N.O.Rajabov “Ipakchilik va tutchilik” Darslik. T.2018 y
- 4.N.Axmedov., S.Murodov. “Ipakchilik asoslari” Darslik. T.1998 y